

Xudoydotov Ramazon Uchqunjon uglu

Bukhara Institute of Natural Resources Management

Annotation. Based on the experiments carried out in this article, information on improving the ecology of the soil using a softening disc device on the base rectifier and increasing the working productivity of the rectifier is covered.

Base phrases: mechanical composition, rectifier, porosity, leveling quality, wheel, technological process, humidity, suspension, working organ (disc).

The ecological leprosy of the natural structure of the soil depends on its physical properties; that is, its mechanical composition, large – small size of particles, porosity, water permeability, air exchange, absence of light, slight amplitude changes in movement.[1]

The mechanical composition of the soil is represented by the relative amount of particles of different sizes. Soil particle (0.2 mm...2 mm), its structure is good, moisture, air is well stored in it; small-particle (0.2 mm...20 μm) in the soil, it will be difficult for moisture and air to pass through, since the porosity of low particles is dense to each other. The density of loamy soils on evicted rural farm land is 1.0...At 1.2 g/cm³, the density of the soil as a result of the Walk of agricultural techniques is 1.35...It rises to 1.55 g / cm³, and its ecological essence decreases. When the soil is compacted in a dry state, the particles crumble, the pores shrink and decrease, the passage of water becomes more difficult, there is less Air [2]. Soil is a genus with the ability to transfer water, retain heat and air, as well as being a life environment for living organisms. Qualitative leveling of irrigated land, one of the environmental measures of soil melioration, can be carried out in practice by improving the working organs of rectifier machines.

Repeated leveling in our region is 30 of the total area every year...35 percent is carried out before planting. Ground leveling work is carried out in the fall, or in early bakhor, using long-base leveling machines of the P-2.8; P-4A; PPA-3.1.

The maneuverability of long-base leveling machines is not high, and their weight is more than 2 tons, as a result of multiple turns of aggregates, the impact of Tractor Wheels on the soil negatively changes, which leads to compaction beyond the agrotechnical norm [3]. Such arable land can be achieved by passing 3-4 times over the surface of the area with existing leveling aggregates to form an agrotechnical demand-appropriate plane. This can lead to impaired soil fertility and soil erosion. To eliminate the above problems, the base rectifier working body was improved by scientists of the Bukhara branch of TIQXMMI. A spherical disc softener is installed on the front side of the leveling bucket, at some point the soil is loosened and the layer - by-layer cuts as a result of which the structure of the soil improves, increasing the operating performance of the aggregate by up to twice the tensile resistance by 7 percent. This is done in one pass with the recommended evolutionarily working part, forming a plane corresponding to the agrotechnical requirement. As a result, soil compaction and erosion are reduced, and harmful substances emanating from the tractor engine are reduced and have little impact on environmental ecology.

Literature used:

1. A.Ergashev. "General ecology", Tashkent. "Uzbekistan" 2003.
2. M.Akhmedzhanov "Planerovka orashaemix zemel" Tashkent.1991g.
3. "Collection of scientific articles of the scientific practical conference on the problems of resource selection in the branches of the national economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan" Bukhara 1993.
4. I.Hasanov., J.Kuchkarov., U.Hasanov useful model" device with a softening disc on a longitudinal rectifier". № FAP 2013 00 85.
18. Egamberdiyev, M. S., Oripov, I. U., Hakimov, S., Akmalov, M. G., Gadoyev, A. U., & Asadov, H. B. (2022). Hydrolysis during hydration of anhydrous calcium sulfosilicate. Eurasian Journal of Engineering and Technology, 4, 76-81.
19. Egamberdiev, M. S., Oripov, I. U., & Sh, T. S. (2022). Development of a Method for Measuring the Layered Moisture State of Concrete and Various Bases. Eurasian Journal of Engineering and Technology, 4, 82-84.
20. Z.Z.Qodirov, I.A.Oripov, A.Tagiyev, G.Shomurodova, & M.Bobirova. (2022). WATER-SAVING IRRIGATION TECHNOLOGIES IN SOYBEAN IRRIGATION, EFFECT OF SOYBEAN ON GROWTH AND DEVELOPMENT. European Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development, 3, 79–84. Retrieved from <https://www.ejird.journalspark.org/index.php/ejird/article/view/33>
21. Isayev S. X., Qodirov Z. Z., Oripov I. O., & Bobirova M. B. (2022). EFFECTS OF RESOURCE-EFFICIENT IRRIGATION TECHNOLOGIES IN IRRIGATION OF SUNFLOWERS ON LAND HYDROGEOLOGICAL CONDITIONS. British Journal of Global Ecology and Sustainable Development, 4, 95–100. Retrieved from <https://journalzone.org/index.php/bjgesd/article/view/55>
22. Qodirov Z.Z, Oripov I.O, & Avezov Sh. (2022). Effect of Drip Irrigation of Sunflower Crop on Soil Meliorative Status. Texas Journal of Agriculture and Biological Sciences, 8, 107–111. Retrieved from <https://www.zienjournals.com/index.php/tjabs/article/view/2382>
23. Khodirov Z, Jumaev J, & Oripov I. (2023). Application of water-saving irrigation technologies in the irrigation of fodder beets grown as the main crop. Texas Journal of Agriculture and Biological Sciences, 17, 34–39. Retrieved from <https://zienjournals.com/index.php/tjabs/article/view/4137>